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Semantic Similarity Based Data Alignment Using Ontology and Swarm Intelligence Based Annotating Search Results from Web Databases

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ABSTRACT

Deep analysis of the SRRs from Web databases (WDB) plays major important role to find exact searching for each user and improve the web pages by analysis results. The number of web pages returned from the WDB is known search result records (SRRs); it consists of the several numbers of pages. These returned web pages results becomes complex to analysis each data unit since it consists of several number of data unit .To overcome the problem of web analysis in earlier work proposes an annotation methods where the data and text unit nodes are converted in the form of table, but in these work the data and unit nodes are not semantically measured labeled .In order to conquer these problem in this paper propose an ontology based data alignment method to Semantically label each data units in the annotated table for each and every SRRs returned from WDBs.

This ontology based data alignment algorithm extract data and text unit nodes

features from the SRRs through PSO and then data are aligned based on the semantically labeled named results from ontology. Then perform the swarm intelligence based ABC algorithm to select best search results from annotated table result through the colony of artificial bees .The colony of the ABC consists of the three major bees such as employed, onlookers and scouts bees. Each and every bee in the ABC selects best annotated search results through the behavior of the ABC for annotated table. Then, for each selected search results annotated it again in different point of the view and combined the dissimilar annotations to anticipate an absolute annotation label intended for it. Our experiments results indicates that the proposed DA-ABC algorithm have high precision and recall result for book application when compare to existing data alignment results.

Keywords: Annotating search results, Semantic similarity, Feature extraction, Artificial Bee Colony (ABC), Data alignment (DA), Search Results Record

(SRR), Web Database, Wrapper Generation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the usage of the web search engines in now a day's several number of the search records are used and returned to the each user with similar content .In web search engines the data are encoded in the form of the HTML pages in web search databases. These types of the database maintained by the user are known as the Web databases (WDB).

A characteristic result page returned beginning a WDB has numerous search result records (SRRs). Each and every one of the SRR contains several numbers of data and text units that represents the real world data entity or data object. It becomes major need for several areas to improve the searching results of the user and their SRRs. For example consider an online shopping system need to maintain several numbers of HTMLS pages and thus needs to define the same book information collected from different sites, The system also need to maintain the ISBN number of the book and their price rate of the book also The system also needs to list the prices offered by each site. Consequently, the system needs to be familiar with the semantic of each one data unit.

Data unit is portions of text with the purpose of semantically characterize individual idea of an entity. It communicates to the importance of a record below a characteristic. It is different from a text node which refers to a series of text enclosed through a pair of HTML tags. It defines the relationship between the data unit and text nodes.

In this research work performs an investigation of the data unit level under the SRR based on the concept of the annotation. It becomes major need for several areas to improve the searching results of the user and

their SRRs. To perform this process it becomes important to maintain the details and find exact searching results from WDB. To accurately extract the information from WDB in SRR, it becomes important to measure the semantic related meaning the each attributes of the concepts or book information, unfortunately in earlier work the semantic relationship between the data units and text unit nodes are not measured in result pages.

The most of the existing work [1-2] essentially allocate labels to everybody HTML text node; methodically assess the associations among text nodes and data units. Early applications necessitate tremendous individual efforts to annotate data units physically, which rigorously boundary their scalability. In this research consider how to repeatedly allocate labels to the data units for each SRR from WDBs.

The main objective of the paper is to improve the web search engine results from SRR records with encoded data and text unit node to annotation of the results into table format. In this paper the SRRs information are extracted by measuring the similarity between the data and text unit nodes from SRRs, then automatically alignment of the data units based on the measurement of semantic relationship between the attributes. Once the data alignment process is completed then select best annotation results from the annotation table using the swarm intelligence based Artificial bee colony optimization algorithm (ABC) for each and every one of the Search Results Records (SRR) from WDBs.

2. BACKGROUND STUDY

In recent years wrapper methods is used to extract the data and text unit nodes from SRR and it is automatically saved into the web database [2-7]. In wrapper based generation method there are two major categories such as wrapper induction and the

unsupervised learning methods .The initial approach which uses a supervised learning methods to extract data unit from web pages based on positive and negatively assigned labels to each examples. Labor-intensive labeling of data is, conversely, employment rigorous and time consuming.

Furthermore, designed for dissimilar sites in the similar location, the labor-intensive category procedure desires to be frequent for the reason that they go behind dissimilar pattern. Illustration wrapper induction systems incorporate WIEN [9], Soft mealy [8], Stalker [4], WL2 [6], [10], etc. It extracts information records in SRRs and removes data beginning the records repeatedly. The ontology-matching. [10] Proposition a small number of further heuristics to carry out the task not including by means of domain ontology.

In adding together, these methods do not extort data from information records. In [12] develops a technique to discover example beginning the HTML tag series of a page. The method makes use of the Patricia tree and series association to discover inaccurate equivalent. Conversely, [11] shows with the intention of its performance are also fragile. Our new method does not use tag strings for alignment but trees, which make use of nested tree structures to carry out a large amount further correct information extraction.

In earlier work [13] develop a two methods to perform the search results records in the efficient manner. On the other hand, they necessitate using numerous pages with the purpose of include comparable data records beginning the equivalent location to discover grammars beginning the pages to mine SRRs. Presumptuous the accessibility of numerous pages include comparable SRRs is a major concern difficulty .

J. Madhavan et.al [14] develops an efficient data extraction method to make use of the exhaustive information from SRRs to

distinguish information SRRs records. It is widespread with the intention of a page through various data records doesn't enclose the whole information of everyone information SRRs record.

W. Liu et.al [15] developed an enhanced wrapper based method in the form of the SRRs records. These particular Web pages are create vigorously and are inflexible to index all the way through conventional crawler based search engines. Extraction of the meaningful formation of data from WDBs is a difficult problem appropriate to the fundamental complicated for the formation of such pages.

3. PROPOSED SEMANTIC SIMILARITY BASED DATA ALIGNMENT USING ONTOLOGY AND SWARM INTELLIGENCE BASED ANNOTATING METHODOLOGY

3.1 DATA ALIGNMENT AND FEATURE EXTRACTION

In this paper initially the proposed work analysis or examine the web data information in deep manner for each SRR which is encoded in the form of the HTML format. In the HTML encoded format page consists of data and text unit nodes .To exactly analysis the results of the data and text unit first the important text and data unit features are need to extract in correct manner .In earlier we use an PSO to extract data and text unit from SRRs pages in WDB, once the data and text units are extracted then measure the semantic similarity of those nodes to perform proper alignment task in the table. Similarity of the data and text unit nodes are measured through ontology algorithm. Before this process first we need to perform several types of correlation amongst one page to a different page are predictable by means of subsequent relationships,

One-to-One Relationship, Each and every text unit from SRRs contains only data unit and it is enclosed by the pair of the tags <A> and .

One-to-Many Relationship, each and every text unit node contains multiple numbers of the data units for SRRs. This assessment is appropriate in widespread because SRRs are generate through pattern programs.

Many-to-One Relationship each data unit multiple number of text units, it is common to style of the HTML tags to trim self-assured information. It is important to remove the irrelevant tags and identify the most important tags in the SRRs therefore that the fullness of every partition data unit be able to be returned.

One-To-Nothing Relationship each and every text unit of the SRRs belongs to text unit category only makes use of the frequency-based annotator to determine pattern text nodes.

3.1.1 FEATURE EXTRACTION USING PSO

To extract feature from the encoded data unit and text unit nodes based HTML form become major difficult task ,in order to perform this process in efficient manner ,in earlier work we proposed an Particle Swarm Optimization based on the behavior of particles .The most important features extracted from this encoded based HTML based SRRs are Data Content (DC), Presentation Style (PS), Data Type (DT), Tag Path (TP), and Adjacency (AD) for WDBs, thus improve search engine results in efficient manner.

Data unit (DU) is defined as set of data from SRRs it is like same as keywords.

Presentation Style (PS) is defined as set of styles supported by each one of the SRRs such as type of the presentation styles are

font size of the text ,size of the each fonts, background color ,text adornment, etc., and whether it is italic or bold.

Data unit from different SRRs belongs to same concept with different types of the presentation style, since each and every one of the search results records are created in HTML encoded format based on the individual interest.

Data Type (DT) is defined as set of different types of the data such as int, float, etc. The successive essential data types are well thought-out based on the moment in time, exchange, numeral, Decimal, Percentage, character, and String.

Tag Path (TP) is defined as set of the text nodes from HTML form and fined the way beginning the source of the SRR to the resulting node in the tag hierarchy structure.

Adjacency (AD) is defined as the results are originated through keywords to search related concepts and discovered from dissimilar SRRs.

3.2 SEMANTIC SIMILARITY MEASUREMENT USING ONTOLOGY

In this research to analysis the search results records data unit and text unit nodes from WDB based on the measurement of the semantic similarity through the roughest theory(RST) based classification ,identifies the exact semantic similarity match based on the separation of the original data and text unit nodes into two sets is named as elementary sets [16]. The semantic similarity measure of the each and every data, text unit nodes are measured based on the characteristics of the attributes and how to solve the data alignment problem also mentioned in OARS [17]. The concept of data units and text units from the HTML pages in RST is demoralized in OARS to compact by way of doubts all the way

through the diagram process of ontology alignment ,it accurately matches the data and text unit correctly which belongs to the same concept.

Algorithm 1 shows the pseudocode of semantic similarity based data alignment method for data and text units. In steps 1 the different similarity measures based features are extracted from PSO. Step 2-6 are used to choose the appropriate attributes of the data and text unit nodes in exact way. Step 7–10 are second-hand to assign a self-confidence quantity to each data and text unit nodes from WDBs with best extracted feature results. Let $[x]_F$ is defined as the matching factor to analysis the similarity between the data and text unit nodes through the following equation (1) to equation (7) with extracted features from PSO.

Let U be the set of unmapped data units in the ontology $U = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n\}$

F be the set of matched factors of each data units in the results $F = \{f_1, \dots, f_n\}$

X be subset of U

f_1 represents the value of $Sim_{text}(d_i, d'_i)$ as defined in(1)

f_2 represents the value of $Sim_{datalines}(d_i, d'_i)$ and $Sim_{hsp}(d_i, d'_i)$ as defined in(2) and (3) respectively

f_3 represents the value of $Sim_{pr}(d_i, d'_i)$ & $Sim_{strc}(d_i, d'_i)$ as defined in (4&5)

f_4 represents the value of $Sim_p(d_1, d_2)$ as defined in (6)

f_5 represents the value of $Sim^p(d_1, d_2)$ as defined in (7)

f_6 represents the value of $Sim^T(d_1, d_2)$ as defined in (8)

The correctness results of the each and every one of the data unit from feature extracted results with set of the data unit is defined as,

$$\alpha_F(X) = \frac{|(X)|}{|F(X)|}$$

3.2.1 TEXT UNIT SIMILARITY

Measuring the text unit based similarity finds the same text unit nodes from different SRRs, and groups them into the single group. It is defined through the analysis of the Smoa parameters.

$$Sim_{text}(d_i, d'_i) = \frac{Smoa(c(d_i, d'_i))}{T \text{ SIMILARITY}} \quad (1)$$

3.2.2 DATA UNIT SIMILARITY

The data unit based semantic similarity between two different data unit nodes of the same text unit nodes is measured using the following conditions:

- $Sim_{datalines}(d_i, d'_i)$ be the linguistic similarity amongst data units in the SRRs pages
- Σ be the exterior resource (WordNet)
- $s(d_i)$ is defined as set of the data units through similar synonyms
- $h(d_i)$ is defined as the set of the data units and hypernyms for data units
- $t(d_i)$ is defined as the set of data units with opposite meaning the data units d'_i

The similarity of data units is measured as,

$$Sim_{datalines}(d_i, d'_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } d'_i \in s(d_i) \\ 0.5 & \text{if } d'_i \in h(d_i) \\ 0 & \text{if } d'_i \in t(d_i) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

3.2.3 DATA CONTENT SIMILARITY

The data content similarity is used to measure the content of the each and every data unit, it is measured based on the following conditions that corresponds to the same concept in SRRs. $Sim_{hsp}(d_i, d'_i)$ be structural similarity among diverse data

units d_i, d'_i . $K_{sup}(d_i)$ with super subset of the classes for different data with same concept d_i

$K_{sup}(d_i)$ is defined as the series of super classes of various data with similar concept d_i

$K_{sup}(d_i)$ is defined as the series of the super classes of cardinality various data with similar concept $K_{sup}(d_i)$

$K_{sup}(d_i)$ is defined as the series of the super classes of cardinality various data with same concept $K_{sup}(d_i)$

$$Sim_{sup}(d_i, d'_i) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{|(K_{sup}(d_i) \cap K_{sup}(d'_i))|}{|K_{sup}(d_i)|} + \frac{|(K_{sup}(d'_i) \cap K_{sup}(d_i))|}{|K_{sup}(d'_i)|} \right) \quad (3)$$

$Sim_{pr}(d_i, d'_i)$ represents the similarity between data units with their properties .

$pr(d_i)$ is defined as the series of super classes of various data properties through similar concept d_i

$pr(d_i)$ is defined as the series of the super classes of various data properties through similar concept d_i

$pr(d_i)$ is defined as the series of super classes of cardinality of various data properties through similar concept d_i

$pr(d_i)$ is defined as the series of super classes of cardinality of various data properties through similar concept d_i

$$Sim_{pr}(d_i, d'_i) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{|(pr(d_i) \cap pr(d'_i))|}{|pr(d_i)|} + \frac{|(pr(d'_i) \cap pr(d_i))|}{|pr(d'_i)|} \right) \quad (4)$$

Finally combine both of this similarity into one

$$Sim^{strc}(d_i, d'_i) = \frac{1}{3} \left(Sim_{hsp}(d_i, d'_i) + Sim_{hsp}(d_i, d'_i) + Sim_{pr}(d_i, d'_i) \right) \quad (5)$$

3.2.4 PRESENTATION STYLE

Presentation style of each and every data units should discover the various styles of units among data units d_1 & d_2

$$Sim_p(d_1, d_2) = \sum_{i=1}^n Ds_i / 6 \quad (6)$$

Where Ds_i is the score of the i^{th} style data type defined by $Ds_i = 1$ if $D_d^1 = D_d^2$ and $Ds_i = 0$ otherwise, and D_d^i is the i^{th} style of data unit d .

3.2.5 TAG PATH SIMILARITY

Tag path similarity is measured based on the measurement of the distance among two parallel text units in the tag tree. Let p_1 & p_2 be the tag paths of d_1 & d_2 , be their corresponding data units and $PLen(p)$ specified as the number of the tags that are specified in the path p association amongst d_1 & d_2 is

$$Sim^T(d_1, d_2) = 1 - \frac{EPT(p_1, p_2)}{PLen(p_1) + PLen(p_2)} \quad (7)$$

3.2.6 ADJACENCY

The adjacency association amongst two different data units d_1 & d_2 is measured based on the path d_1^p & d_2^p and the presentation style d_1^s & d_2^s , among the data unit

$$Sim_A(d_1, d_2) = \frac{Sim'(d_1^s, d_2^s) + Sim'(d_1^p, d_2^p)}{2} \quad (8)$$

Algorithm 1: Data alignment for data and text units

Input: $D = \{d_1, d_2, d_3, \dots, d_m\}$, a set of unmapped data units from the source ontology; $D' = \{d_1', d_2', d_3', \dots, d_m'\}$, a set of unmapped data units from target ontology $F_1 = F, F = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n\}$ a set of matching data units, $n=6$

Output: Aligned units (d_i, d_j, c) where c is the best confidence degree

1. For $k=1$ to 6;
2. For $i=1$ to m ;
3. For $j=1$ to n ;
4. Compute $\alpha_f = 1$ THEN
5. ALIGN (d_i, d_j')
6. IF $F_k = F_i$ then
7. $C=1$
8. Else
9. $C=0.8$
10. End if
11. End if
12. End for
13. End for

3.3 ARTIFICIAL BEE COLONY FOR BEST ANNOTATION RESULTS

Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) algorithm [18-19] is one of the most important swarm intelligence algorithm based on the behavior of the bee, it consists of the three major bees such as employed bees, onlookers and scouts. In order to perform to select best annotation results from the annotated table, initially the first half of the annotated results is taken as input to the employee bee and other hand the remaining half of the bee is taken as input to onlooker bee process. The total number of the employee bee which is equal to the total no of annotated results in the SRR around the hive. In ABC algorithm,

a best annotated search results represents through the position and its position values of the annotated search results web pages results from semantic similarity is updated based on the fitness function.

The first step the population is generated from annotated search results records $x_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, SN)$ (no of annotated web search results) is a D -dimensional vector. Here, D is the number of optimization parameters results for SRRs. After initialization, the of search results annotated search results table of the results are found based on the maximum number of iteration for each of the annotated table population, $C = 1, 2, \dots, MCN$, through the bees. If the result found in the employee bee stage is achieved within the iteration it is kept as memory in the first stage or else it is not considered as the best annotated search results. Similarly if the nearest annotated search result table is better than the earlier results it is updated in the memory, or else the position of the earlier one is updated. An onlooker bee evaluates decides the annotated web search results tables' information taken from all employed bees and chooses results based on the probability p_i through the following expression:

$$p_i = \frac{fit_i}{\sum_{n=1}^{SN} fit_n} \quad (9)$$

where fit_i is the fitness value of the optimized annotated search results solution i and SN is size of the population. Produce the candidate the annotated food source based on the following expression,

$$x_{ij}^{new} = x_{ij} + \phi_{ij} (x_{ij} - x_{kj}) \quad (10)$$

Where $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, SN\}$ and $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, D\}$ are randomly chosen indexes, ϕ_{ij} is a random number between $[-1, 1]$. Thus, as the search approaches to the optimum solution in the search space, the step length is adaptively reduced. In this

work, the value of the parameter is not achieved in the limit the current annotated search results is not considered as the best results and it is removed in the scout bee stage, founded new annotated search results are obtained from the scout bee with x_i , it can be defined as in,

$$x_i^t = x_{min} + rand(0,1)(x_{max} - x_{min}) \quad (11)$$

After each candidate optimized search results source position v_{ij} is produced its performance is compared with the existing annotated search results from employee bee, if achieves better than it is replaced with earlier results in the memory, it is kept as the best annotated search results.

Detailed pseudo-code of the ABC algorithm is given below:

- 1: Initialize the population of solutions $X_{ij}(i = 1, \dots, SN, j = 1, \dots, D)$
- 2: Evaluate the population
- 3: cycle=1
- 4: **repeat**
- 5: Produce new solutions v_{ij} for the employed bees by using and evaluate them
- 6: Apply the greedy selection process
- 7: Calculate the probability values P_{ij} for the solutions x_{ij}
- 8: Produce the new solutions v_{ij} for the onlookers from the solutions x_{ij} selected depending on P_{ij} and evaluate them
- 9: Apply the greedy selection process
- 10: Determine the abandoned solution for the scout, if exists, and replace it with a new randomly produced solution x_{ij}

11: Memorize the best solution achieved so far

12: cycle=cycle+1

13: **until** cycle=MCN

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In the way to measure the accuracy of the proposed data alignment algorithm with the artificial bee colony optimization algorithm for SRRs WebPages from the WDBs for book applications, is web search databases is automatically extracted through WISE i Extractor [20-21]. Some most important term in the book application is selected as a keyword and it is given as input to search process for each domain. The performance of the proposed DA-ABC and the existing system is measured in terms of the precision and recall. Precision is evaluated based on the division of the properly connected data units better than every one of the aligned units through the scheme is represent as:

$$Precision = \frac{tp}{(tp + fp)} \quad (12)$$

Recall is evaluated based on the division of the data units which are properly aligned throughout the scheme for every data units of actually aligned data units through the individual data unit is represented as ,

$$Recall = \frac{tp}{(tp + fn)} \quad (13)$$

Figure 5: Semantic similarity measurements

In the Figure 5 shows the semantic similarity based ontology measurement for data and text unit that corresponds to book domain, based data and text unit nodes are extracted results.

domain, based data and text unit nodes are extracted results.

Figure 7: Annotation wrapper

In the Figure .7 shows the annotation wrapper results with artificial bee colony based optimization results for book domain, based data and text unit nodes are extracted results.

Figure 6: Data alignment

In the Figure 6 shows the unalignment annotation results of results for book

Figure 8: Comparison Graph

In this graph Figure 8 measure the performance of the annotation of the search result records in the clustering with existing

results and the Ontology based search result records alignment phase with optimized (ABC) search results records ,it shows the proposed system have highest best precision and recall result in the results .

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, presents an efficient data alignment algorithm and the best annotation approach for each data and text unit nodes for SRRs .In the proposed work each and every data units in the web pages are automatically annotated through the measurements of the semantic similarity based on the ontology and then perform annotation approach using wrapper methods Each one of the annotation methods annotate the data unit the table exact manner after the data alignment results from the ontology. Best analysis of the annotated results still becomes problem in order to solve this difficulty in this paper presents an ABC based optimization algorithm to select best annotation results from the annotated table. The most important research of the proposed methods is that the results are automatically returned from the web database. This proposed method is able to handle the large Web database through the variety of the semantic relationship is mentioned for each and every encoded data and text unit nodes from HTML.

5.1 FUTURE WORK

In future work we apply the split complex text node through the supporting of additional explicit operators and apply different classification methods to derive the values of the semantic similarity measurement that can recognize the best method to the data alignment problem.

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